

Density and viscosity studies of sucrose and maltose in 0.5 M aqueous ammonium chloride solutions at 25, 30, 35 and 40°

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Viscosity data of sucrose and maltose solutions in water and in 0.5 M aqueous ammonium chloride at 25, 30, 35 and 40° are analysed with the help of modified Jones-Dole equation and the density data are analysed with the help of Redlich-Meyer equation. The apparent molar volume of transfer from water to aqueous ammonium chloride is also calculated. Results show that sucrose and maltose act as structure-makers in water and in aqueous ammonium chloride.

It has been reported¹ that nonionic solutes along with ionic ones can effect structural changes in different solvents. These structural interactions of carbohydrates with electrolyte substance in aqueous and non-aqueous solvents are very important for investigating their physicochemical properties. Studies on transport and thermodynamic properties have been made on aqueous and non-aqueous ternary systems containing carbohydrates and electrolytes².

Ammonium and alkyl substituted ammonium salts are known to influence the conformational stability of proteins³ and amino acids⁴ in solutions, hence a systematic study of the influence of ammonium chloride on volumetric and viscometric behaviour of sucrose and maltose is of current interest. Both these properties are sensitive to specific interactive charges in solution. Here, apparent molar volumes and viscosities of sucrose and maltose in water and in 0.5 M aqueous ammonium chloride solution are reported.

Results and Discussion

The observed densities (ρ) of the solutions, which are the mean of three or four series of many measurements, at 25, 30, 35 and 40° are used to calculate apparent molar volumes (Φ_v) of the sugars using equation (1),

$$\Phi_v = M/\rho_0 - [1000(\rho - \rho_0)/(C\rho_0)] \quad (1)$$

where ρ_0 is the density of water, and 0.5 M aqueous ammonium chloride solution, ρ the density of sugar solutions, M the molecular weight of sugar and C the concentration (mol dm⁻³). In slightly concentrated solutions of electrolytes or solutions containing spherical particle, Φ_v varies linearly with C and could be least-square fitted to the Redlich-Meyer equation⁵,

$$\Phi_v = \Phi_v^0 + S_v C \quad (2)$$

where Φ_v^0 is the limiting apparent molar volume of the sugars and S_v the experimental slope. The regression coefficients of equation (2) for sucrose and maltose in water and in 0.5 M

Table 1. Φ_v^0 , S_v and σ of maltose and sucrose solutions in water and in aqueous 0.5 M NH₄Cl at different temperatures

Parameter	25°	30°	35°	40°
Maltose in water				
Φ_v^0	216.29	216.32	216.37	216.48
S_v	1.767	1.831	1.773	2.252
σ	0	0	0	2.9×10^{-5}
Maltose in aqueous 0.5 M NH ₄ Cl				
Φ_v^0	253.18	253.42	253.80	254.03
S_v	1.026	0.997	1.011	1.101
σ	0	0	0	1×10^{-5}
Sucrose in water				
Φ_v^0	211.22	211.26	211.31	211.36
S_v	1.677	1.739	1.781	1.970
σ	7.07×10^{-5}	0	0.3×10^{-5}	0
Sucrose in aqueous 0.5 M NH ₄ Cl				
Φ_v^0	248.17	248.37	248.54	248.91
S_v	3.937	3.941	4.100	4.120
σ	3×10^{-5}	0	0	0

aqueous ammonium chloride at all the four temperatures along with standard deviations are included in Table 1. The Φ_v^0 values of sucrose and maltose in water as well as in 0.5 M aqueous ammonium chloride are positive. However, those in 0.5 M aqueous ammonium chloride are slightly higher than those in water. This suggests that both these sugars are hydrated electrostatically in pure water through dipole-dipole interactions of OH groups of sugars with surrounding water

molecules. In ternary system (water + sugar + NH₄Cl), the interactions of NH₄⁺ and Cl⁻ ions with polar groups (OH) of sugars reduce electrostriction of sugars by water resulting in an increase of Φ_v^0 .

The temperature dependence of Φ_v^0 of sucrose in water and in 0.5 M aqueous ammonium chloride can be expressed by equations (3) and (4) respectively,

$$\Phi_v^0 = 211.21 + 1.679 \times 10^{-5} T + 5.547 \times 10^{-5} T^2 \quad (3)$$

$$\Phi_v^0 = 247.62 - 0.151 \times 10^{-5} T + 7.259 \times 10^{-5} T^2 \quad (4)$$

Similarly, the temperature-dependence of Φ_v^0 of maltose in water and in 0.5 M aqueous ammonium chloride can be expressed by equations (5) and (6) respectively,

$$\Phi_v^0 = 216.10 - 1.210 \times 10^{-4} T + 2.029 \times 10^{-4} T^2 \quad (5)$$

$$\Phi_v^0 = 252.67 + 1.89 \times 10^{-4} T + 9.994 \times 10^{-4} T^2 \quad (6)$$

The apparent molar expansibility, $\Phi_E^0 = (\delta\Phi_v^0/\delta T)$, calculated from equations (3-6) has been found to increase with temperature (Table 2) suggesting caging effect⁶. The

Table 2. Limiting apparent molar expansibility (Φ_E^0) for maltose and sucrose solutions in water and in aqueous 0.5 M NH₄Cl at different temperatures

Sugar	25°	30°	35°	40°
Maltose in water	2.89×10 ⁻²	3.44×10 ⁻²	3.99×10 ⁻²	4.54×10 ⁻²
In aq. 0.5 M NH ₄ Cl	1.35×10 ⁻²	1.35×10 ⁻²	1.64×10 ⁻²	2.23×10 ⁻²
Sucrose in water	2.75×10 ⁻³	3.29×10 ⁻³	3.84×10 ⁻³	4.38×10 ⁻³
In aq. 0.5 M NH ₄ Cl	3.63×10 ⁻²	4.35×10 ⁻²	5.08×10 ⁻²	5.81×10 ⁻²

structure-making/breaking tendency of sucrose and maltose could be ascertained from the sign of $(\partial^2\Phi_v^0/\delta T^2)_p$. Accordingly, positive values of $(\partial^2\Phi_v^0/\delta T^2)_p$ for both the sugars in water as well as in 0.5 M aqueous ammonium chloride make them structure-makers.

The $\Phi_{v(tr)}^0$ values for sugars calculated from the relation,

$$\Phi_{v(tr)}^0 = \Phi_v^0(\text{aq. NH}_4\text{Cl}) - \Phi_v^0(\text{aq}) \quad (7)$$

have been found to be positive (Table 3) suggesting that there is a decrease in volume shrinkage due to electrostriction of sugars by the solvent in the presence of NH₄Cl.

Table 3. Apparent molar volumes of transfer ($\Phi_{v(tr)}^0$) of maltose and sucrose at different temperatures

Sugar	25°	30°	35°	40°
Maltose	36.89	37.10	37.43	37.54
Sucrose	36.96	37.11	37.22	37.54

The relative viscosity (η_r) data of sucrose and maltose

solutions in water as well as in 0.5 M aqueous ammonium chloride are analysed with the help of equation of the type⁷,

$$\eta_r = 1 + BC \quad (8)$$

The representative graph of η_r vs C for both the sugar solutions in water and in aqueous ammonium chloride at 25° are represented in Fig. 1. Similar plots have been obtained at other temperatures. The slopes of the plots (Fig. 1) yield B -coefficients.

Fig. 1. Plots of η_r vs concentration (C) for sugar solutions : (○) maltose in water, (●) maltose in aq. 0.5 M NH₄Cl, (⊕) sucrose in water and (●) sucrose in aq. 0.5 M NH₄Cl.

The B -coefficient is a measure of solute-solvent interactions and it depends on the size and shape of the solute

Table 4. Viscosity B -coefficients for maltose and sucrose in water and in aqueous 0.5 M NH₄Cl at different temperatures

Temp. °C	In water	In aq. 0.5 M NH ₄ Cl
	Maltose	
25	0.863	1.057
30	0.902	0.950
35	0.885	1.093
40	1.008	1.038
	Sucrose	
25	0.983	1.107
30	0.913	0.936
35	0.861	0.846
40	0.720	0.784

molecule. The B -coefficients of aqueous sugar solutions are positive (Table 4) indicating the presence of solute-solvent interaction through dipole-dipole interaction of OH groups of sugars with surrounding water molecules. For ternary system (sugar + water + NH_4Cl), positive B values (Table 4) are higher than those in aqueous solutions, suggesting increased structure-making tendency of sugars in presence of ammonium chloride.

Temperature variation has no systematic effect on B -coefficient.

Experimental

Ammonium chloride (AnalaR) was recrystallised from conductivity water and dried under reduced pressure at $\sim 80^\circ$ for 12 h. A 0.5 M solution of ammonium chloride was prepared in conductivity water. Maltose (99.9% pure, John-Baker) and sucrose (99.9% pure, AnalaR) were used as such. These sugars were dissolved in water and in 0.5 M aqueous ammonium chloride to yield solutions of required molarities. The solutions were allowed to stand for some time before every measurement so as to avoid air bubbles.

Density was determined using a 15 cm³ double arm pycnometer⁸ (accuracy ± 0.00001 g cm⁻³). The viscosity was measured using a Ostwald-Sprengel type viscometer⁹ (accuracy $\pm 0.1\%$). Density and viscosity measurements were carried at 25, 30, 35 and 40° in a thermostated water bath ($\pm 0.01^\circ$).

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